

Approaches to Politeness Theories

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Abstract

This study is conducted to consider the approaches to politeness theories (The Classical Approach and The Discursive Approach). It exclusively introduces these two approaches and comprehensively informs when they are proposed, who the concerned linguists are and how are they criticized and progressed. This paper consists of three sections, which are the introduction, the approaches to politeness theories and the conclusion. The introduction is devoted to identify approaches to politeness theories (classical approach and discursive approach) and briefly introduces the classical linguists and the discursive linguists as well as presents their own ideas and proposes. The approaches of politeness theories maintains the classical approach, which is mainly criticized of adopting a universal framework and of avoiding the role of cultural differences and the impact of context on the utterances' interpretation. Although the classical linguists and their proposes have been utterly criticized by a group of linguists (discursive linguists), they have paved the way to the discursive linguists to overcome the problems that result from drawing on a universality model of data interpretations. This paper comprehensively considers the discursive approach. In this section, it figures out the relationship between politeness and impoliteness, clarifies the notion of 'face' from the perspective of the discursive approach, and identifies the methodology that is proposed by the discursive linguists. Finally, section three presents the most concluding points that have been driven throughout conducting this study. This paper critically considers the views that have been raised by the classical linguists or by the discursive linguists in order to avoid all the problems that face researchers while the process of data analysis or interactions' interpretation. In the other words, this paper provides the researchers with the most credible way that helps the process of interactions' interpretations in general and in terms of politeness in specific.

Keywords: *Politeness Theories, Traditional Approach, Discursive Approach, Impoliteness, Discursive Methodology*

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1. Introduction

The theories that have been adopted by linguists to analyse or to interpret interactions are mainly classified into two main approaches: the classical approach and the discursive approach. The classical approach (or some called the traditional approach) considers politeness from a generalised perspective that ignores the role of cultural differences and the impact of context on the interpretation of interactions, whereas the discursive approach takes the contextual factors and the cultural differences into consideration to analyse interactions in terms of politeness.

The use of the theories that are categorised as classical approach dates back to the seventeenth of the last century when a group of theories proposed to analyse interactions in connection to politeness, such as Lakoff's politeness rules (1973), Grice's Co-operative Principle (1975), Brown and Levinson's politeness strategies (1978, 1987) and some other theories. This approach has been criticised by a group of linguists due to the ignorance of the impact of culture and the influence of the contextual factors on the analysis of politeness. These linguists are recognised as discursive theorists, namely: Sara Mills, Richard Watts, Derek Bousfield and many more linguists that generally believe that researchers need to consider all the factors that affect interactions to have an accurate analysis of interactions. Moreover, to fulfill this need, researchers need to draw on authentic interactions rather than invented examples or expressions out of context.

The aim of this study is to provide the researchers that are interesting in conducting qualitative studies on the authentic interactions in general and in terms of politeness in specific with an adequate methodology that can result in a reliable data collection and an accurate data analysis, which consequently brings about an accurate result. Thus, this paper is very helpful for the researchers to get familiar with the approach that they may adopt before conducting any study. Moreover, it illustrates all the steps that researches need for conducting empirical part of the studies that are associated with examining daily authentic interactions. This requires observation of all the factors that affect the daily interactions such as, gender, power, culture, context, intonation, and many more.

1. Approaches to politeness theories

Approaches to politeness studies can be classified into the traditional approach and the discursive approach. The traditional approach that considers politeness from a universal perspective encompasses Lakoff's politeness rules (1973), Grice's Co-operative Principle (1975), Brown and Levinson's politeness strategies (1978, 1987), and Leech's politeness principle (1983). The discursive approach is concerned with the interactants' perception and the role of culture and context in the analysis of interactions. Discursive linguists, such as Ide (1989, 1992), Spencer-Oatey (2000), Mills (2003), Watts (2003), Bousfield (2008), Culpeper (2011), and many others either have improved on the traditional approach or adopted different arguments. Before considering the discursive approach and theorists, the main arguments of the classical

1.1 The Classical Approach

The theorists that represent the classical approach to politeness were essentially helpful in establishing a basis for politeness studies. Grice (1975), Lakoff (1973), Leech (1983), and Brown and Levinson (1978, 1987) are theorists who investigate politeness from the *etic* perspective; that they adopt a generalized approach to consider politeness without regarding the impact of cultural differences.

Grice (1975: 45) considers "rational" realisation of interaction and cooperative contribution of interactants as two basic principles of maintaining appropriate communication. She believes that interactants should cooperate as much as possible while interacting (Grice, 1975: 45). Grice's *cooperative principle* considers language from an ideal perspective, which is completely different from actual interactions, because interactants may be uncooperative, but still have polite interactions. Grice proposes four conversational maxims ("quality", "Quantity", "Relation", "Manner") as a condition of having polite interaction; that if interactants flout the maxims, their interactions will cause offence (Grice, 1975:45-6). This generalisation is not accurate, because interactants may be, for example, irrelevant and still polite.

Lakoff used politeness rules to refine some negative aspects that emanated from Grice's cooperative principles. She tried to connect the analysis of politeness with the impact of cultural norms. Lakoff tried to go beyond the conceptual notion of politeness² (Politeness as linguistic terms) by showing the role of culture in constructing polite interactions, because she regarded politeness as "equivalent to what most people in our society consider 'polite' behaviour... and we are used to it" (Lakoff,1990: 35). For Lakoff (1973: 298), ("Don't impose", "Give options", "Be

friendly”) are the rules that represent the notion of “Be polite”. According to Eelen (2001:49), these rules exist in all languages and “capture directly ordinary speakers’ politeness1 evaluations”; for instance, Lakoff’s first rule ‘*Don’t impose*’ is concerned with maintaining appropriate cultural interactions. However, Lakoff does not make a clear distinction between politeness1 (politeness as daily interactions) and politeness2.

The problems that are associated with Lakoff’s politeness arguments are associated with considering politeness from a systemised and a universal perspective. Lakoff (1990: 34) defines politeness as “a system of interpersonal relations designed to facilitate interaction by minimizing the potential for conflict and confrontation inherent in all human interchange”. Recognizing politeness as a *system* is one of the crucial problems that Lakoff’s theory of politeness suffers from.

Politeness is not the process of following a recommended system, but it is associated with the interactants’ intention and interpretation, because: 1) interactants can produce polite interactions drawing on personal choices, i.e. without applying a specific system; 2) following a designed system cannot always guarantee a polite interpretation by recipients. Another shortcoming that is associated with Lakoff’s view is that: she sees politeness as a strategy of minimizing face threatening by proposing three politeness rules. This strategy does not always result in polite interactions, because it only focuses on the role of speakers and their intentions without taking the role of recipients’ interpretations and the impact of culture differences into consideration. In the other words, although these rules operate in all languages and they can observe cultural norms, they do not consider cultural differences. According to Eelen (2001: 2), cultures may vary in prioritizing a specific rule over another in producing polite interactions; for example, “European cultures tend to emphasize Distancing strategies” (rule 1, *Do not impose*), “Asian cultures tend to be Deferential” (rule 2, *Give options*), whereas “modern American culture tends towards Camaraderie” (rule3, *Be friendly*). Thus, drawing a boundary between politeness as universal linguistic phenomena and politeness as daily interactions was not fulfilled in Lakoff’s politeness rules.

Leech, like Grice and Lakoff, also associated politeness to the notion of *conflict avoidance* by proposing a general framework. However, he brought *interpersonal rhetoric* into the analysis of interactions. Leech (1983: 56-7) makes a distinction between semantics and pragmatics; that he associates ideational function to semantics, whilst he connects the i“nterpersonal” and the “textual” functions to pragmatics. Semantics is associated with the logical meaning of the

sentences, whereas Pragmatics is associated with the interpretative meaning of interactions (Leech, 1980: 2). Leech (1983: 57) believes that “interpersonal and textual” are factors that determine the process of constituting interactions and message conveying.

This modification is a good attempt by Leech to consider the process of language constitution and language analysis from the perspective of contextual differences and the impact of interactants’ perception. However, Leech (1983: 132) claims that generally polite interactions are recognized by applying "politeness principles" (*Tact, Generosity, Approbation, Modesty, Agreement, and Sympathy maxims*). Thus, although by proposing "politeness principles" and distinguishing the logical meaning of utterances (Semantics) from the interpretative meaning of them (Pragmatics) Leech shows the significance of the interpretative meaning of utterances in the process of identifying politeness, he adopts the same generalised system that does not result in accurate assessment of interactions.

This generalisation also dominated Brown and Levinson’s politeness theory. For Brown and Levinson (1987), politeness is a matter of "conflict and avoidance"; and the crucial themes are 'Rationality' and Face', which are considered as universal characteristics. *Rationality* is associated with making use of logic (Brown and Levinson, 1987: 64), whereas *face* is “something that is emotionally invested, and that can be lost, maintained, or enhanced, and must be constantly attended to in interaction” (Brown and Levinson, 1987: 61). Brown and Levinson tried to engage interactants’ mental and psychological roles in determining the nature of interactions. However, they could not avoid their politeness theory from being generalised due to dependence on a fixed calculation to indicate politeness and impoliteness.

Brown and Levinson (1987) make a connection between Grice’s Cooperative Principle and the notion of face. For Brown and Levinson (1987: 62) face is composed of both negative face (the want is “unimpeded by others”) and positive face (the want is “desirable to at least some others”). One of the critical problems that classical approach suffers from is associated with the use of the notion of “face”, because as Spencer-Oatey (2000:12) clarifies, face is considered as “a universal phenomenon”, which gives the sense that “everyone has the same fundamental face concerns”. Thus, Spencer-Oatey (2000:12) proposes “rapport management” which “examines the way that language is used to construct, maintain, and/or threaten social relationships and includes the management of sociality rights as well as face.

Brown and Levinson argue that some speech-acts threaten hearer's face (Brown and Levinson, 1987: 65). Therefore, they propose four strategies that perform FTAs which are "baldly" strategy, "positive politeness", "negative politeness" and "off record" strategy (Brown and Levinson, 1987: 69).

Baldly: is associated with the process of doing FTAs "in the most direct, clear, unambiguous and concise way possible" (Brown and Levinson, 1987: 69).

Positive politeness: "is oriented toward the positive face of H, the positive self-image that he claims for himself" in a way that "S considers H to be in important respects 'the same' as he" (Brown and Levinson, 1987: 70).

Negative politeness: "is oriented mainly toward partially satisfying (redressing) H's negative face" which is recognised by "self-effacement, formality and restraint, with attention to very restricted aspects of H's self- image" (Brown and Levinson, 1987: 70).

Off-record politeness: It is associated with "all kinds of hints as to what a speaker wants or means to communicate, without doing so directly, so that the meaning is to some degree negotiable" (Brown and Levinson, 1987: 69).

Another shortcoming of Brown and Levinson's study of politeness is associated with considering politeness from the perspective of speech acts, whilst every piece of interactions may be offensive, polite or any other neutral interactions. Brown and Levinson (1987: 76) propose that politeness should be observed in relation to social variables such as Power (P), distance (D) and cultural rank

(R). They compose a formula to show how speakers choose a specific strategy for their interactions. In the following calculation, x = the degree, w= weightiness of FAT, H =hearer and S = speaker.

$$WX = D(S,H) + P(H,S) + RX \quad (\text{Brown and Levinson, 1987: 76})$$

According to Brown and Levinson (1987: 76), the degree of face threat can be calculated by the above formula which attempts to illustrate how social variables, such as the nature of relationship among interactants, the social power and social rank affect the constitution and interpretation of interactions. These variables affect the interactants' perception of interactions. For example, the nature of relationship between the speaker and the hearer is one of the variables that the degree of face threat weightiness that results from using direct order draws on. If the

speaker and the hearer are close friends, the degree of weightiness of face threat are less compared to a case if they were just classmates. However, this formula can never accurately measure the degree of polite or impolite interactions because there are many other factors (such as, culture, context, content, setting, the interpretation and the perception of interactants and many others) that play a role in determining the nature of interactions. Therefore, the same interaction by the same interactants can have different interpretations.

The classical approach has failed to provide a satisfactory theory that can help researchers to conduct politeness studies. Classical theorists are to some extent aware of the impact of context and social variables on interactions' constitution and perception, but they do not go beyond generalisations in their recommended frameworks and rules. On the other words, classical theorists do not take the impact of cultural differences, personal perceptions, situations and settings into account. Thus, it is hard to predict the nature of interactions according to universal frameworks that could be applicable to all languages and cultures, because there are many issues that need to be considered in assessing them, such as the cultural specifics, the personal criteria, the situation, the content of interactions, the setting of interactions, and the nature of relationship among interactants and many others. Over all, analysing polite interactions according to generalised frameworks, such as Grice's Cooperative principle, Lakoff's polite rules, Leech's Politeness principles, and Brown and Levinson's politeness strategies bring about inaccurate results.

According to Brown and Levinson (1987: 13), "the notion of 'face'...consists of two specific kinds of desires...: the desire to be unimpeded in one's actions (negative face), and the desire (in some respects) to be approved of (positive face)". Brown and Levinson associate face restrictedly with the individuals' wants (negative or positive) which implies that standing against individuals' desires results in losing face. This stance is not always applicable because having a negative response to the others' wants may cause no offence, because the nature of an interactant's desire will determine the consequence of impeding this desire. For instance, impeding the desire of getting a job opportunity usually causes no offence.

2.2 Discursive Approach to Politeness theories

Discursive theory is associated with considering all the elements that affect the language constitution and the utterance interpretation. Discursive theorists "have brought contextual

factors into the analysis of politeness” (Pan, 2011: 71). They believe that the constitution and the interpretation of interactions is not rule-governed, i.e. it is impossible to assess the nature of interactions drawing on generalised frameworks, so researchers need to observe all the factors that affect interactional constitution and interpretation, such as personal, cultural, situational and contextual influences (Mills, 2003; Watts, 2003; Culpeper, 2011).

Discursive theorists agree that politeness or impoliteness “is not located at the level of the utterance, as it seems to be for Brown and Levinson” (Linguistic Politeness Research Group, 2011: 2). Nevertheless, Culpeper (2010: 3235) states that “the general focus of the discursive approach is on the micro, that is, on participants’ situated and dynamic evaluations of politeness, not shared conventionalised politeness forms or strategies”. Thus, discursive theorists recommend researchers to consider interaction as a part of a whole context rather than as a detached utterance, in order to result in an accurate assessment of politeness and impoliteness. The meaning of an utterance inside the context is usually different from the connotative meaning of that utterance outside the context. Moreover, utterance can have different interpretations in different contexts.

Mills (2011: 28) argues that “post-modernism might be seen as a type of theoretical move which questions all concepts and evaluations and is skeptical of all attempts at grand narrative or metanarrative, that is, all overarching theories which attempt to generalise or universalise”. Discursive theory is concerned with the process of enquiring interactions in all related aspects in order to have the most proper interpretation of interactions. This theory puts an end to the traditional approach that consider politeness from a generalised perspective. Therefore, this theory urges researchers to take all the related elements of interactions into consideration in order to conduct accurate studies on interactions. For instance, to conduct a study on politeness or impoliteness according to discursive approach, researchers need to examine the utterances in context. So, they need to: 1) observe interactants in terms of gender, power, distance, psychology, physiology as well as cultural, religious, ethnic and ideological backgrounds; 2) discern the interactional situation in respect of settings, the nature of interactional event and external factors; 3) interpret the utterances in terms of content, purpose, surface meaning and implied meaning. Mills (2011: 30) states that although all discursive theorists have tried to improve the method of analysis of both politeness and impoliteness, they are mainly divided into two groups in which “the first group makes use of the other theoretical aspects to revise Brown and Levinson’s politeness theory, whilst the second group proposed their own theories”. These attempts came

after traditional theory's deficiency in terms of distinction between politeness¹ and politeness², methods of data collection and process of data analysis.

The Linguistic Politeness Research Group (2011:5) states that with the advent of the discursive approach the emphasis has converted "from analysing politeness as a system of rational choices made by a model speaker, to an analysis of the way that choice about what counts as politeness or impoliteness are made in particular contexts". Generalisation in the analysis of interactions is inaccurate because each culture or each group of practice has its own norms that determine the nature of interactions. For example, English people have different traditions in terms of making offers compared to Kurdish people.

Mills (2011: 35) argues that discursive linguists agree on three essential aspects. "firstly, discursive theorists share a view of what constitutes politeness (particularly ...that politeness does not reside in utterances...). secondly, discursive theorists try to describe the relation between individuals and society in relation to the analysis of politeness; thirdly, discursive theorists tend to use a similar form of analysis" by placing emphasis on contextual analysis, the impact of culture on the text, the assessment of interaction, and interactants' perceptions. All these arguments are very helpful to consider while conducting a study in order to adopt a reliable methodology for data collection and have an accurate analysis of data.

Theorists, such as Spencer-Oatey (2000: 3) and Watts (2003: 8) believe that utterances usually derive their meaning from the contexts that they are used in, therefore, they could not be categorized, out of context, as polite, impolite interactions. Spencer-Oatey (2000: 3) states that "sentences or linguistic constructions are not *ipso facto* polite or rude; rather, politeness is a social judgement, and speakers are judged to be polite or rude, depending on what they say in what context". Although some expressions are intrinsically formulated to demonstrate polite (such as, generous, lovely, respectful and many others), or impolite impressions (such as, motherfucker, silly, foolish and many others), they can have different interpretation in different contexts.

According to Eelen (2001: 236), "Bourdieu's sociological insights can be combined with insights from discursive psychology" in order to consider discursive approach to politeness in a correct basis. Bourdieu's sociology maintains that "all cultural symbols and practices, from artistic tastes, style in dress, and eating habits to religion, science and philosophy-even language itself- embody interests and function to enhance social distinctions" (Swartz, 1997: 6). But Discursive Psychology places emphasis on "the nature of knowledge, cognition and reality: with how events

are described and explained, how factual reports are constructed, how cognitive states are attributed” (Edwards and Potter, 1992: 2). Nevertheless, it operates on the basis that “mental states become relevant, as a form of social action which is oriented to interactional and inferential concerns” (Wooffitt, 2005: 89), which involves “memories, knowledge, attitudes, beliefs and motives” (Haugh, 2011: 257). Thus, discursive approach to politeness needs to consider the analysis of discourse from the perspective of both sociology and psychology in order to observe all the external (social) and internal (psychological) concerns.

Discursive Theorists pay attention to the process of evaluation. According to Mills (2011: 40) “discursive theorists tend to focus on process rather than product; that is, these theorists are interested in the choices which could have been made and the possibilities of misunderstandings, rather than assuming that politeness is a given and a product”. The aim of the discursive theory is to concentrate on the process of the data analysis by recommending the issues that researchers need to consider for bringing about accurate interpretations rather than the nature of interpretations themselves. According to Watts (2003:23) “it is impossible to evaluate (im)polite behaviour out of the context of real, ongoing verbal interaction”. Discursive theorists try to go beyond the assumption that draws on generalised frame works to distinguish polite expressions from impolite one, because they believe that the meaning of interactions will be derived from the context. Mills (2011: 43) adds that discursive linguists broaden the scope of politeness studies at the level of individual and social variables; for example, investigating politeness in association with gender, power, distance, and settings.

Discursive linguists have greatly contributed in the process of identifying politeness and impoliteness, introducing useful theories to illustrate how polite and impolite interactions work, and how they are constructed and how should be assessed as well as proposing useful research methods in terms of collecting data and their analysis. Thus, the views and the arguments of some of the outstanding discursive linguists would be shed light on in terms of the aforementioned issues.

2.2.1 Face in Discursive Approach

Face is a very significant notion in the study of politeness and impoliteness. The notion of *Face* is used by Goffman to represent the public identity that everyone claim. According to

Goffman (1972: 5), face is "the positive social value a person effectively claims for himself, by the line others assume he has taken during a particular contact". Goffman, in his definition, concentrates on positive social values without considering positive cultural, psychological and personal principles of interactants in maintaining face during interactions, because face is maintained due to positive social, cultural, personal and psychological status that everyone would like to achieve during interactions. Moreover, Culpeper (2011: 25) argues that "face is not confined to the immediate aspects of an individual's self (e.g. abilities, disposition, appearance), but includes all that the self identifies with (e.g. family, school, possessions)". The concept of face can have a very extensive notion because it represents individuals' personal values and their belonging feelings to family, cultural, ethnic and religious as well as their ongoing situational stances and interests.

Moreover, Spencer-Oatey (2000: 13) believes that the notions of *positive* and *negative face* which have been identified by Brown and Levinson are insufficient, because the "conceptualization of positive face has been underspecified, and that the concerns they identify as negative face issues are not necessarily face concerns at all". Therefore, to replace the notion of face and its aspects, Spencer-Oatey (2000: 13) proposes the notion of *rapport management* "the management of harmony-disharmony among people" which consists of two essential aspects that are "the management of face and the management of social rights".

Spencer-Oatey (2000: 14) points out that "face is associated with personal/social value, and is concerned with the people's sense of worth, dignity, honour, reputation, competence and so on". While, "sociality rights [...] are concerned with personal/social expectancies, and reflect people's concerns over fairness, consideration, social inclusion/exclusion and so on". Observing interactants' wants and rights to manage social relations while interacting is the duty of *rapport management*. Thus, *rapport management* illustrates how interactions operate to devalue or enhance the rapport in order to maintain the intended interaction.

Spencer-Oatey (2000:14) argues that "Quality face" and "Identity Face" are two aspects of face. For Spencer-Oatey (2000:14), *Quality face* is associated with personal efficiencies that people strongly consider them, such as "competence, abilities, appearance, etc. [sic]", whereas *Identity face* is about the values that people usually try to maintain "in terms of social or group roles" and in connection with their "sense of public worth". Moreover, Spencer-Oatey (2000:14) proposes that Sociality rights are divided into "Equity rights" and "Association rights". Spencer-Oatey (2000:14) states that "Equity rights" is associated with the interactants' expectations of receiving

deserving rights from their counterparts, whereas “Association rights” is concerned with the observation of the nature of relationship that interactants need to interact accordingly.

Spencer-Oatey took a great step to sort out how interactions work and how they need to be analysed. Thus, via proposing *rapport management*, she recommends interactants to realise interactions accurately that could be rapport threatening in order to adjust their interactions accordingly to maintain smooth communication.

According to Eelen (2001:159), “Every human being has ‘face’; cultures only differ in when and how face can be threatened or redressed. Likewise, each culture has the notion of an FTA; the difference lies in what utterances qualify as FTAs”. Eelen (2001:159) attempts to clarify that everyone all over the world has a face but the nature of interactions that cause face losing may vary from one culture to another due to differences in cultural norms. Unlike Eelen’s argument, Terkourafi argues that “individuals alone do not ‘have’ face and cannot ‘gain’ or ‘lose’ face. Rather face² [sic] is grounded in the interactional dyad. Without an Other to whom they may be directed, face concerns cannot arise” (Terkourafi, 2008: 52). For Terkourafi, face is always associated with interactions but not interactants, because she believes that interactants intrinsically have not face, but it is the interactions that construct face. Eelen (2001) and Terkourafi (2008) look at the notion of ‘face’ from different angles, therefore the combination of these two views can bring about a better understanding of the notion of face. Hence, face is a universal concept that derives its values, attributes, principles and frame from the external factors, such as counterparts, situation, setting and context and from the personal factors, such as personal feeling, vision, criteria and ideology. Thus, it may vary from one culture to another and from one person to another.

Bousfield (2008: 42) believes that “face is individually (internally, cognitively, historically) expected by the Self but is interactional (externally, mutually, continuously) constituted between Self and Other”. The notion of face is not only associated with the internal feeling of the interactants, but it also emanates from external factors, such as the situation, the place, the content of interactions. Unlike Brown and Levinson’s (1987) assumption that both positive and negative face are of equal significance and use in all cultures, Bousfield (2008: 37) states that “the type, quantity, strength and salience of different aspects of face will vary from culture-to-culture, discourse-to- discourse and, of course, context-to-context”. Each culture has its own particular traditions, customs and norms that consequently affect the process of interaction. For example, conservative societies usually tend to be positive- face cultures, because people usually are harmonious, whereas secular cultures tend to be negative-face cultures because people are less complimentary. Moreover, although face is a universal concept in connection to politeness and impoliteness, they differ from one culture to another because their components can have different attribute, nature and the influence strength.

Bousfield (2008: 42) states that “constitution of the face of one member of a group can have an impact on the face constitution and face expectation of other members of a group”. External factors are essential to the process of face constitution. These factors may include the interaction’s ongoing situation, the nature of relationship among interactants, the personalities of interactants and their common interests which are all helpful to facilitate mutual impact on each other’s face, i.e. Interactants can play a part in composing face for each other; consequently, they affect each other’s face. However, people outside their group of interaction might also influence the face of interactants, because each person may belong to more than one group, consequently a part of a person’s face might be constituted in accordance with prevailing atmosphere of another group different from the ongoing interactional group.

2.2.1 Politeness1 and Politeness2:

Eelen (2001) places emphasis on the distinction between *politeness1* and *politeness2*, and between politeness and impoliteness as well as proposing a process for conducting politeness studies. Eelen (2001: 51-2) states that although Brown and Levinson’s effort is not merely to consider politeness as a linguistic phenomenon (*politeness1*), which can be noticed “when discussing negative politeness strategies”, they could not make a clear distinction between *politeness1* and *politeness2*. According to Eelen (2001: 31), the differentiation between *politeness1* and *politeness2* should not be only considered in terms of concepts, “but rather the relationship between both notions should be carefully monitored throughout the entire analytical process-not only at the input stage”. The distinction of everyday interactions from politeness linguistic concepts is one of the main achievements of discursive approach, because this distinction is crucial to make use of linguistic politeness theories in the analysis of interactions within a specific context.

Eelen (2001: 38) argues that “politeness₁ is always an instance of everyday social life, and as a social practice it will always be geared towards, or at least have, some social effect”. Since politeness₁ is concerned with everyday interactions, it may involve both volitional and discernment interactions; therefore politeness₁ is not always affected by cultural norms. Concerning politeness₂, Eelen (2001:43) argues that “politeness₂ should concern the scientific conceptualisation of the social phenomenon of politeness in the form of a theory of politeness₁. By means of such theory we should be able to understand how politeness₁ works, what its functionality is, what it ‘does’ for people and for society in general”. Although politeness₂ is essential to gain a general insight into politeness studies via recommended theoretical concepts, it does not always provide politeness studies with concepts that could be applicable in all cultures. For example, the concept of politeness could not have the same definition in all cultures: if politeness is rather concerned with keeping “distance” in “British culture”, it is more about giving “deference” in “Japanese culture” (Kádár and Mills, 2011: 4). Thus, politeness linguistic concepts may share some common vision in all culture, but they may differ in some respects from a culture to another.

According to Eelen (2001: 47), “unlike politeness₁, which is restricted to the polite end of the polite-impolite continuum, politeness₂ should cover the whole range of the continuum”. Politeness₂ is concerned with daily interactions which involves both polite and impolite utterances. However, using (im)politeness₂ would be more accurate because it is more comprehensive. Watts (2003) uses *first order politeness* and *second order politeness* instead of *politeness₁* and *politeness₂*. For Watts (2003: 10), “‘politeness₂’ means something rather different from our everyday understanding of it and focuses almost uniquely on polite language in the study of verbal interaction”. Thus, both Eelen (2001) and Watts (2003) present that politeness₁ is associated with the linguistic theoretical part that considers politeness. According to Watts (2003:9), the distinction of politeness₂ from politeness₁ has lunched when “social scientists lift the term ‘(im)politeness’ out of the realm of everyday discourse and elevate it to the status of a theoretical concept in what is frequently called Politeness Theory”.

Considering politeness from a universal perspective is one of the serious problems that discursive linguists have tried to solve by examining politeness from its actual context of interaction through making a distinction between politeness₁ and politeness₂

Eelen (2001:35) proposes that the concept of “politeness-as-practice” can be used instead of *politeness1*, which is associated with everyday polite interactions. According to Eelen (2001:35), *politeness-as-practice* is divided into three different kinds, which are: “*expressive*” that is (associated with offers, compliments, refuses, etc. ...), “*classificatory*” which is (associated with the interactants’ assessment) and “*metapragmatic*” which is (associated with interactants’ understanding on politeness).

One of the serious issues that Eelen (2001) argues that in order to achieve accurate results researchers should avoid themselves from directly using concepts of politeness 2 to investigate into everyday polite interactions; instead Eelen suggests that researchers should move from politeness1 to politeness2. In the other words, moving from *emic* to *etic* helps researchers to understand the actual meaning of daily interactions in its ongoing context, consequently this understanding contributes to bring about the distinction between politeness1 and politeness2 is helpful to realise the process of conducting studies on politeness and impoliteness. Particularly, Geyer (2008: 32) asserts that “a critical assessment of the politeness1/politeness2 dichotomy leads directly to an examination of how politeness is realised in discourse. At the same time, questions remain as to what aspects of politeness1 should receive primary attention, how politeness1 can be examined, how the relationship between politeness1 and politeness2 should be addressed”. This distinction makes politeness researchers gain a deep insight into interactions in its ongoing context to observe the impact of cultural and personal distinctions while conducting studies on politeness or impoliteness.

2.2.3 Discursive Methodology

Discursive theorists have made a noticeable change in the process of collecting data and its analysis. Classical works on politeness considered politeness from generalised perspectives. Grice’s (1975) maxims, Lakoff’s (1973) rules, Leech’s (1983) politeness Principles, and Brown and Levinson’s (1987) politeness strategies associate the production of polite interactions with a set of recommended patterns that flouting them will cause offence. In contrast to the classical views, discursive theorists (e.g. Mills (2003), and Watts (2003), Bousfield (2008)) believe that the

interpretation of interactions depends on interactants' intentions and perceptions in accordance with the actual contexts of interactions.

Concerning data collection, discursive theorists believe that making use of natural interactions is essential. Mills (2003:10) and Eelen (2001:39) recommend researchers to depend mainly on authentic interactions for collecting data. Mills (2003: 44) states that "there is often a mismatch between what people think they do, or should do, and what they actually do", because according to Eelen (2001:39), "people never identify with impoliteness", i.e. interactants may not communicate normally if they were aware that they would be taken as samples of a study. For instance, if a researcher depends on questionnaire for collecting data in terms of politeness or impoliteness, s/he will fail to access natural data consequently s/he will not be able to bring about reliable findings. This problem to some extent may also occur while recording interactions. For example, inviting a group of colleagues to have dinner and inform them that all their interactions will be recorded for conducting a study in terms of politeness, the interactants will try to use polite patterns and avoid offensive interactions at least for a couple of minutes until they get used to this situation. Therefore, researchers usually face difficulties in collecting reliable data for carrying out a study.

Thus, for collecting authentic interactions to the maximum extent, the researcher could follow some measures. Firstly, although researchers cannot record others' interactions without asking permission due to research ethics, they have to avoid telling the participants the topic of the study. Secondly, they should try to engage the participants with the ongoing conversation to forget that their speeches are being recorded. Thirdly, according to Mills (2003: 13), providing the analysis of the recorded interactions with anecdotes is very important, because "anecdotes give us an insight into the role of stereotype and show us the ways in which people make assessments of politeness". In the other words, brief narrative statements should support the transcription of the recorded interactions in order to help analysers to gain better insights into interactions; consequently, they can do better analysis and assessments of transcribed interactions.

Mills (2003:122) also argues that impoliteness should be studied separately from politeness due to differences in the factors that they result from. Because "'politeness' always refers to the 'polite' end of the polite-impolite continuum, it never covers impolite forms of behaviour" (Eelen,

2001:41). Politeness and impoliteness are two contradictory aspects of language use; therefore, it is not an academic stance to regard impoliteness as the absence of politeness or vice versa, because each type has its own particular basis, structure and attributes that require to be studied independently from each other. Impoliteness is an ignored field of language that needs to be considered side by side of politeness although Culpeper and Bousfield present two outstanding works on impoliteness.

Mills (2003:33) prefers to make use of “a form of analysis which questions the autonomy of the individual” instead of “the model speaker in linguistic analysis”, because she believes that speakers are usually associated with “a range of communities of practice where they negotiate their position and their gender, race, and class identities”. According to Mills (2003: 30), although members of a community of practice share some attributes, they do not exactly have the same contribution in interactions, because each one of them can have a different background that emanates from other *communities of practice*, i.e. even the members of the same *community of practice* can have different interests and backgrounds. Mills (2003:38) states that discursive approach is in a severe need for a “process-oriented view of conversation”, because interactional observers need to follow systematic deductive process that consider all the issues that have impact on language constitutions as well as their assessments.

According to Culpeper (2011: 104), rules “are driven by social norms and conventions”, he adds that “it is also quite possible to have rules that people habitually ignore”. However, it is important to consider the nature and the attributes of any culture before measuring the effects of its customs on the interactants. Therefore, the idea of categorizing customs absolutely or semi-absolutely as rules is not applicable to all cultures. In conservative societies, such as Kurdish society customs and traditions are strictly adopted by people to function like rules or sometimes stronger than rules, whereas other societies, especially culturally diverse societies do not pay a great attention to the customs, and consequently customs are probably weaker than rules.

Terkourafi (2001: 25; 162) believes both classical and discursive linguists generally adopt theory-based approach, because they collect and analyse data from a theoretical perspective, whilst she argues that interactions should be considered from the perspective of “frame-based approach”. Terkourafi (2005: 247) clarifies that “frame-based view” is concerned with the strategy

of considering a huge amount of data, that collected in various places, situations, and occasions with the participation of a large number of interactants that have different social statuses, ages, gender, power, and interests in order to bring about an accurate result. Although social variables and habits play essential role in determining the nature of interactions, it is not adequate to restrict the assessment of interactions according to a frame-based criteria, and to ignore rational assessment, because personal conscientiousness and individual criteria are also crucial.

3. Conclusion

1. The classical theorists could not go beyond generalisations in their recommended frameworks and rules. They do not take the impact of cultural differences, personal perceptions, situations, and settings into account. They just proposed some generalised frameworks, rules, principles, and strategies to analyse interactions, whereas it is impossible to predict the nature of interactions, because drawing on universal frameworks could not be applicable to all languages, contexts, and cultures.
2. The discursive theory considers all the elements that have impact on the language constitution and on the utterances' interpretation. The concerned linguists believe that the constitution and the interpretation of interactions are not rule-governed, rather they depends mainly on the speakers' intention and the recipients' interpretation.
3. Researchers need make distinction between politeness¹ which is about everyday interactions and Politeness² which is concerned with the linguistic concepts before conducting studies on politeness. This distinction is crucial to make use of an accurate linguistic politeness theory in the analysis of interactions within a specific context.
4. To bring about an accurate result while conducting a study: 1. researchers need to make use of authentic interactions in the process of data collection, such as recording natural interaction; 2. To engage the recipient, the speaker or both of them in the process of data analysis.

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